

CANDIDATES TEACHERS' CLASSROOM MANAGEMENT SELF-EFFICACY LEVELS

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Abstract:

This research aimed to determine the classroom management self-efficacy beliefs of students have been studying in Faculty of Education and students have been maintaining pedagogical formation certificate program. It employed survey model. The study group was composed of 362 trainees who attended to pedagogical formation certificate program in Duzce University in 2015/16 academic year spring term and 255 sophomores, junior and senior class students in Classroom Teaching and Science Teaching Departments in Duzce University Faculty of Education in 2015/16 academic year. In the study, it was aimed to reach the whole population and a scale was implemented instead of sampling. The research was conducted with 410 returning scales. "Teacher Self-Efficacy Scale" was conducted in order to determine the classroom management self-efficacy perceptions of the student teachers. Since the data were not normally distributed, Mann-Whitney U Test which is a nonparametric test. The following results were obtained: Classroom management self-efficacy perceptions of the students who have been studying in Faculty of Education and students who have been attending the pedagogical formation certificate program are high in terms of "Providing the student participation", "Utilization of Teaching Strategies" and "Classroom management". The difference between the classroom management self-efficacy perception averages of the two groups was not statistically meaningful. Also, there was no statistically meaningful difference between the students who have been studying in Faculty of Education and students who have been attending the pedagogical formation certificate program in terms of gender variable.

Keywords: Student teacher, self-efficacy, pedagogical formation certificate program

1. Problem Status

Self-efficacy has been defined as the self evaluation of the capacity that a person feels and the cognitive process that people develop about their capacities to complete a task. It has been regarded as an important motivational item that affects many behaviour and performance results. For instance, self-efficacy is observed when a mathematics teacher believes that he can teach algebra successfully to his students. In some resources (Wayne and Cecil, 2012), self-efficacy is named as self-effectiveness but it is used as self-efficacy in most of the resources. Therefore, self-efficacy notion will be used in the present study. According to Bandura (1993), self-efficacy determines the amount of effort and time that an individual will spend on a target. Accordingly, the more people believe in their capacities, the more their efforts increase. When the individual performances are observed in terms of self-efficacy, the following results are obtained: individuals who have stronger beliefs on their skills are more successful and insistent. Therefore, self-efficacy is associated with the performance displayed in productivity, hard tasks, career choice, learning, acquisition and compliance with the technology (Wayne and Cecil, 2012).

As Bandura (1980, 1986) defined, self-efficacy is the individual's decision on their capacity to complete a task successfully. In other words, it refers to the individual's belief of completing a hard task in the future. An individual with higher perceived self-efficacy puts more effort into any task than an individual with less perceived self-efficacy. Also an individual with high perceived self-efficacy is more willing to try and experience new things. People with high perceived self-efficacy can control the environment, accordingly they are not afraid to try something new. On the contrary, if the self-efficacy belief of an individual is less than his actual competence, the individual may fail to use his capacity effectively and tend to be inactive and lazy (Senemoglu, 1997). As previously mentioned, self-efficacy covers one's perception of accomplishing a task, therefore it affect one's choices, efforts, anxiety and trust levels. Individuals with more self-efficacy always endeavor to be competent (Aydin, 2013).

Self-efficacy is regarded as the basic concept of social learning theory and it means one's self-consciousness after they realize the required performance and their capacity to accomplish it. It refers to the self awareness and self-belief of an individual. Individuals with higher self-efficacy can handle complicated issues, solve problems, appear to be more patient, believe in their success and be more competent in their professional lives. On the other hand, individuals with lower self-efficacy fail to cope with important issues, experience hopelessness and unhappiness, find themselves incapable to solve the problems, avoid to try again after a failure and believe that their effort would not chance the results (Korkmaz, 2006). It is clear that people are more

motivated and successful when they believe that they have the potential to achieve their goals (Ormrod, 2014).

Considering the education and teachers, the educational quality mainly depends on the quality of the teachers. Teachers should be competent and sufficient. A teacher cannot fulfill the responsibilities of teaching without vocational competency (Acat, 2006). A teacher is mainly responsible for training students with enough knowledge that makes them successful in the information age. The teacher should be qualified with enough capacity to fulfill this responsibility and the conditions should be convenient accordingly. At this point, teachers should have enough information about teaching field, teaching profession, educational system and educational policies. A teacher who does not possess enough information and perception about the key issues in the field fails to act as a professional. Therefore, teacher training should be rearranged according to the paradigm shifts occurred in science, information and education (Ozden, 2006).

The teacher should act as a classroom leader instead of an officer who is responsible for performing the teaching program. Especially the constructivist approach implemented in education have separated the roles of the teacher from the traditional ones. These roles have cooperative, reflective, participative and interdisciplinary features. These are also the requirements of teacher training programs. In constructivist educational environments, teachers no longer have the disciplinary, informative roles. Instead they act as an individual who facilitates learning, a counsellor who provide guidance to the students and a leader who helps the students focus on their goals. They exhibit a manner that enhances the communication and cooperation in the classroom (Acat, 2006).

Management is generally defined as the effective and adequate utilization of the material and human resources in the organization with the aim of accomplishing the organizational goals (Aydin, 1991; Bursalioglu, 1994). Classroom management is a subfield of the educational management and it can be defined as the implementation of the educational management on a specific area. Also, the classroom management is regarded as a tool that enables qualified learning and teaching. Therefore, it occupies an important place in educational studies. Yet the success and productivity of the teaching depends on how well the classroom is managed. According to Erdogan (2000), no matter how professionally the teaching is organized, success is only possible with a managed classroom.

The classroom is the centre of the educational process. For this reason, classroom conditions and effective management of the classroom have great importance. Classroom management is a tool that enable students to understand, evaluate and control themselves (Celep, 2000). Classroom management includes providing convenient conditions to learning, removing the obstackles for teachers and students,

effective usage of time, providing the participation of the students and management of the material and human resources in the classroom (Erdogan, 2000). As Tasdemir (2000) stated, the aim of the classroom management is to improve the learning quality. Teacher focuses on attracting the students' attention instead of conveying the information. He prepares the educational setting, leads to new ways that facilitate learning and provides informative counselling. The teacher's responsibilities are to teach how to learn, to guide, and to lead students to think, research, learn and use the information. Teachers should start the in-class communication and maintain it in a strong and healthy way. They should use the classroom environment and equipment effectively and provide students' participation with the help of their clothing, voice, eye movements and body language (Babadogan, 2006). Teacher is the preparer of the educational conditions, also he constitutes a part of it (Erturk, 1979; Basar, 1999). He is responsible for the arrangement of the information and environment in the classroom (Kaya, 2006). Whether teaching is a science or an art has been debated for many years. Both opinions have supporters. According to the ones who regard teaching as an art, skills, intuition, creativity and inspiration are important. On the other hand, the ones who regard teaching as a science place importance on information and skills. In modern education, the following roles are expected from the teacher: Being a teaching expert, being incentive, possessing managerial roles, having leadership skills, being a counsellor and a role model (as cited from Woolfolk, 1990, Özdemir, Yalın, Sezgin, 2004). The researchers detected strong relationships between self-efficacy of the teacher which enhances students' success and the teacher behaviours (Wayne and Cecil, 2012).

As previously mentioned, according to self-efficacy theory, academic motivation depends on individual's belief to be successful. Thus the individual accomplishes tasks that he regards as easy and achievable (Borich, 2014).

The findings obtained from the self-efficacy studies applied in schools demonstrate that self-efficacy is related to educational attainment, examination results, students' motivation, teachers' applications, supervisors' scorings and classroom management strategies of the teachers. According to Bandura (1997), the stress that people experience in the most challenging situations affects their self-efficacy beliefs, their efforts and time that they spend on solving the problems. Therefore, helping teachers develop their self-efficacy beliefs at the very beginning of their professional lives enhances their improvements in the long run (Wayne and Cecil, 2012). In order to strengthen the self-efficacy beliefs of the individuals, the people around them (e.g. teachers and students in an educational institution) should encourage them and express their support verbally. Also the success of the peers in a particular task encourages the individuals. In order to provide this, successful educators may appear as a role model in the educational institutions. Thus the individual is most likely to demonstrate similar

successful performances. Last factor is the previous success or failure experiences of the individual in the profession. The self-efficacy belief that the individual has once possessed affects the effort, constancy and success levels of him in the following tasks (Bandura, 1986; Borich, 2014). Accordingly, student teachers should experience success especially during the teaching practice in their undergraduate studies and during the candidatedship in the first years of the profession.

The legal status of the teachers in Turkey was arranged in accordance with The Ministry of National Education the law no. 1739. The legislation states that teaching is a profession which covers the education and related managerial duties of the government and that teachers are responsible for fulfilling these duties in line with the aims and principles of Turkish National Education. According to the law, preparation to the teaching profession is carried out with general knowledge, field training and pedagogical formation. However, with the new managerial arrangements, pedagogical formation training is available for almost all graduates of various faculties. Therefore discussions over the quality of the teacher candidates have occurred lately. Whether the teacher candidates believe that they have enough knowledge and skills required for classroom management and whether they think that they can accomplish teaching responsibilities should be determined. The aim of the research is to determine the classroom management self-efficacy beliefs of the undergraduate students of Faculty of Education and the students who have been attending the pedagogical formation certificate program. The questions to be examined in the research are given above.

2. Problem Statement

What are the self-efficacy beliefs of the undergraduate students of Faculty of Education and pedagogical formation students in terms of classroom management?

2.1 Sub Problems

- What are the self-efficacy beliefs of the undergraduate students of Faculty of Education in terms of classroom management?
- What are the self-efficacy beliefs of the pedagogical formation students in terms of classroom management?
- Is there any significant difference between the self-efficacy beliefs of the undergraduate students of Faculty of Education and pedagogical formation students in terms of classroom management?
- Is there any significant difference between the classroom management self-efficacy beliefs of the undergraduate students of Faculty of Education and pedagogical formation students in terms of gender variable?

2.2 Research model

The survey model was conducted with the aim of determining the self-efficacy beliefs of the undergraduate students of Faculty of Education and pedagogical formation students. Survey models are research approaches that aim at representing a past or a present situation directly. The research topic, individual or object is sought to be defined regarding its own conditions and characteristics. No effort is given on changing or affecting them in any way (Karasar, 2011:77).

2.3 Population and Sampling

The research population consists of 362 pedagogical formation certificate program trainee in Düzce University in 2015-16 academic year spring term and 255 sophomore, junior and senior class students in Classroom Teaching and Science Teaching Departments in Duzce University Faculty of Education in 2015/16 academic year. Sampling method was not adopted in the study. Reaching the whole population was targeted and the scale was applied to the whole population. The research was carried out with 410 scales after they have been examined. The data obtained from the teacher candidates who participated in the research was given in Table 1.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics

Variables	Sub variables	N	%
Student	Pedagogical Formation Student	206	50,02
	Undergraduate Student	204	49,08
Gender	Female	305	74,4
	Male	105	25,6

The three quarters of the teacher candidates participated in the research are female and one quarter of them are male. The current distribution demonstrates that the gender distribution of the population is proportional. The number of undergraduate students and pedagogical formation students are close to each other.

2.4 Data Collection Tool

“Teacher Self-efficacy Scale” developed by Tchannen-Moran, Woolfolk-Hoy (2001) was conducted in the research. The scale was adapted to Turkish by Cakiroglu and Sarikaya (2005) (as cited from Korkut, 2012). Also the factor analysis of the scale was carried out by Korkut (2012). Low points in the scale indicate low self-efficacy of the teachers and high points indicate high self-efficacy. The scale consists of 3 factors as providing the student participation, using the teaching strategies, classroom management and also 24 items. According to the measurements carried out by Korkut (2012), the reliability

coefficients were determined as .82, .86 and .84 for the factors and .93 for the whole scale. The score intervals used for the interpretation and rating of the average points are as follows: 0-0.80 (never), 0,81-1.60 (slightly), 1.61-2.40 (some), 2.41-3.20 (quite), 3.21-4.00 (extremely). The reliability rates of the data collection tool measured for the present study are given in Table 2.

Table 3: The reliability rates of the data collection tool

Sub dimensions	C. Alfa
Providing the student participation	0,647
Using the teaching strategies	0,736
Classroom management	0,689
Total	0,769

The reliability rates states above indicate that the scale is quite reliable.

2.5 Data Analysis

Kolmogorov-Smirnov and Shapiro-Wilk normality tests were applied in order to examine the normality of the data set. It is observed that the results deviated from the normality in a significant degree. In line with the results, Mann-Whitney U test which is one of the nonparametric tests was chosen to be applied. The significance level was determined as p .05 in all statistical operations.

3. Findings and Interpretation

1. The findings of the classroom management self-efficacy beliefs of the undergraduate students on Faculty of Education and the pedagogical formation program students are given on Table 3.

Table 3: Descriptive statistics of the scale sub-dimension points

	n	$\bar{x}$	ss
Providing the student participation	410	3,93	,496
Using the teaching strategies	410	3,96	,578
Classroom management	410	3,98	,564
Total	410	3,95	,546

As presented in the table, the self-efficacy beliefs of the undergraduate students of Faculty of Education and pedagogical formation students are at the high level in terms of "Providing the Student Participation ($\bar{X}=3,93$)", "Using the Teaching Strategies (X

"=3,96)" ve "Classroom Management ($\bar{X}=3,95$)". As previously stated, self-efficacy is the individual's belief of success and his opinion of fulfilling the required actions for the targeted results. Considering that there has been detected a strong relationship between the teacher self-efficacy belief and teacher behaviours, the current results indicate that high self-efficacy beliefs of the teachers have great importance. According to the results, the high self-efficacy beliefs of the teacher candidates who participated in the research demonstrate that they believe in their success in teaching profession and that they will endeavour to solve the problems and to be role models.

2. The findings about whether there is a significant difference between the classroom management self-efficacy beliefs of the undergraduate students of Faculty of Education and the pedagogical formation students

Mann-Whitney Test was applied in order to examine the classroom management self-efficacy beliefs of the teacher candidates in terms of being a undergraduate student and a formation student variable. The results are given in Table 4.

Table 4: Examination of the scale sub-dimension points in terms of being a undergraduate and formation student variable

Dimensions	Education	N	Mean Rank	Total Rank	M.W.U	*p
Öğrenci Katılımı Sağlama	Formation Student	6	197,41	40666	19345	3
	Undergraduate student	20				
Using the Teaching Strategies	Formation student	6	212,61	43797	19548	1
	Undergraduate student	20				
Classroom management	Formation student	6	215,81	44457	18887	6
	Undergraduate student	20				

* p<.05

As demonstrated in the table, the difference between the averages of the classroom management self-efficacy beliefs of the undergraduate students of Faculty of Education and the pedagogical formation program students was not found statistically significant ($p>0.05$). Therefore, the results indicate that the classroom management self-efficacy beliefs are similar regardless of being a undergraduate or a formation program student

variable. According to the results, the classroom management self-efficacy beliefs of the pedagogical formation program students are close to the self-efficacy beliefs of the undergraduate students. It can be stated that both groups (pedagogical formation certificate program group and faculty of education group) believe that they have enough capacity to work successfully and that they have positive personal evaluations in terms of classroom management. It can be inferred from the results that teacher candidates will deal with complicated situations, solve problems, be patient in their studies, have self-confidence to achieve their goals, be more successful in their professional lives and possess positive attitudes in the classroom management process.

3. The findings about whether there is a significant difference between the classroom management self-efficacy beliefs of the undergraduate students of Faculty of Education and the pedagogical formation students in terms of gender variable

Mann-Whitney Test was applied in order to examine the classroom management self-efficacy beliefs of the teacher candidates in terms of gender variable. The results are given on Table 5.

Table 5: Examination of the scale sub-dimension points in terms of gender variable

Dimensions	Gender	N	Mean Rank	Total Rank	M.W.U.	*p
Providing the Student Participation	Female	305	209,58	63920	14769	,243
	Male	105	193,66	20334		
Using the Teaching Strategies	Female	305	206,95	63120	15569	,671
	Male	105	201,28	21134		
Classroom Management	Female	305	202,62	61800	15135	,401
	Male	105	213,86	22455		

* p<.05

According to Table 5, the difference between the averages of the classroom management self-efficacy beliefs of the undergraduate students of Faculty of Education and the pedagogical formation program students in terms of gender variable was not found statistically significant ($p>0.05$). The current result indicates that the gender variable does not make any significant difference in the classroom management self-efficacy beliefs of the teacher candidates and that the both genders have similar perceptions about the classroom management self-efficacy.

According to the results, it can be stated that the classroom management self-efficacy of the male and female undergraduate students of Faculty of Education and male and female pedagogical formation program students are similar to each other. It can be said that male and female groups have positive attitudes towards classroom

management and believe that they have enough capacity to work successfully. The result indicates that the gender variable does not have any effect on the classroom management self-efficacy beliefs of the teacher candidates. It can be concluded that the low and high levels of classroom management self-efficacy beliefs may stem from other factors such as information, pre-learning, experiences, background knowledge etc.

4. Results

The following results were obtained in the present research which aimed at determining the classroom management self-efficacy beliefs of the undergraduate students of Faculty of Education and the pedagogical formation program students:

1. The classroom management self-efficacy beliefs of the undergraduate students of Faculty of Education and the pedagogical formation program students are at high levels in terms of "Providing the Student Participation", "Using the Teaching Strategies" and "Classroom Management". The fact that the classroom management self-efficacy beliefs of the teacher candidates participated in the research are high indicates that they believe in their professional success, they will get through the complicated situations and they will strive to be role model educators.
2. There difference between the averages of the classroom management self-efficacy beliefs of the undergraduate students and pedagogical formation students was not found statistically significant. This result demonstrates that the teacher candidates will be more successful in their academic and professional lives and that they will have positive attitudes and higher performances in the future.
3. The difference between the averages of the classroom management self-efficacy beliefs of the undergraduate students of Faculty of Education and the pedagogical formation program students was not found statistically significant in terms of gender variable. It was detected that the classroom management self-efficacy beliefs of the male and female students of the two groups are similar to each other. It can be concluded that both male and female groups have positive self-evaluations and self-beliefs on their capacity to work successfully in the classroom management process.

References

1. Acat, B. (2006). Yenilenen ilköğretim müfredatı. okul yönetimlerini geliştirme programı, Ankara: İlköğretim Genel Müdürlüğü.
2. Aydın, D. (2013), Sosyal öğrenme kuramı, eğitim psikolojisi (Editör: M. Engin Deniz). Maya Akademi, 5. Baskı. 323-324.

3. Aydın, M. (1991). Eğitim yönetimi, 3. Baskı, Ankara: Hatipoğlu Yayınevi.
4. Babadoğan, C. (2006). Bir insan (öğretmen) olarak müdür. okul yönetimlerini geliştirme programı, Ankara: İlköğretim Genel Müdürlüğü.
5. Bandura, A. (1980). Self-referent thought: the development of self-efficacy. J. Flavell and L.D. Ross (Eds). Cognitive Social Development: Frontiers and Possible Futures. New York: Cambridge University Press.
6. Bandura, A. (1986). Social foundations of thought and action. Englewood Cliffs, Nj: Prentice-Hall.
7. Bandura, A. (1993). Perceived self-efficacy in cognitive development and functioning. Educational Psychologist, 117-48.
8. Bandura, A. (1997). Self-efficacy: the exercise of control, New York: Freeman.
9. Başar, H. (1999). Sınıf yönetimi, Ankara: MEB Yayınları.
10. Borich, G., D. (2014). Etkili öğretim yöntemleri. 8 Baskı. (Çeviri Editörü: Bahaddin ACAT). Ankara, Nobel Yayınları.
11. Bursalıoğlu, Z. (1994). Okul yönetiminde yeni yapı ve davranış. Ankara: Pegem A Akademi.
12. Celep, C. (2000), Sınıf yönetimi ve disiplin, Ankara: Anı Yayınları.
13. Eisenberger, J. (2005). Self-efficacy: Raising the bar for all students. Larchmont, NY: Eye on Education.
14. Erdoğan, İ. (2000). Sınıf yönetimi, İstanbul: Sistem Yayıncılık.
15. Gist, M., E ve Mitchell, T., R. (1992). Self-efficacy: a theoretical analysis of its determinants and malleability. Academy of Management Review, 17 (2), 183-211.
16. Hoy, Wayne K. ve Miskel, G. Cecil (2012). Educational administration, theory, research and practice, (Çeviri Editörü: Selahattin Turan) Ankara, Nobel Yayınları 7. Baskı.
17. Jeanne Ellis, Ormrod (2014). Human learning/ öğrenme psikolojisi. (Çeviri Editörlüğü Mustafa BALOĞLU). Ankara, Nobel Yayınları 6. Baskı
18. Karasar N. (2002). Bilimsel araştırma yöntemi. Ankara: Nobel Yayınları.
19. Kaya, Z. (2006). Öğretim teknolojileri ve materyal geliştirme. Ankara: Pegem A. Yayıncılık.
20. Korkmaz. S.(2006). Sosyal öğrenme kuramı, eğitim psikolojisi, (Editör: Binnur Yeşilyaprak). Pegem A yayıncılık 3. Baskı.
21. Korkut, K. (2009). Sınıf öğretmenlerinin öz-yeterlik inançları ile sınıf yönetimi beceri algıları arasındaki ilişki. Burdur: Mehmet Akif Ersoy Üniv. Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü (Yayınlanmamış Yüksek Lisans Tezi)
22. Özdemir, S. Yalın, İ., Sezgin, F. (2004). Öğretmenlik Mesleğine Giriş. Ankara: Pegem A. Yayıncılık.

23. Özden, Y.(2006). Eğitimde dönüşüm: eğitimde yeni değerler.(6. Baskı) Ankara: Pegem A. Yayıncılık.
24. Robbins S., P. ve Judge, T. A (2012). Örgütsel davranış, (Çeviri Editörü: İnci Erdem) Ankara, Nobel Yayınları 14. Baskı.
25. Robbins, S., P. Decenzo, D., A, Coulter, M. (2013). Fundamentals of management (Çeviri Editörü: Adem Öğür) Ankara, Nobel Yayınları 13. Baskı.280-281.
26. Senemoğlu, N. (1997). Gelişim, öğrenme ve öğretim. H:Ü. Eğitim Fakültesi, Eğitim Bilimleri Bölümü yayınları. 235-242.
27. Slavin, E. R. (2013). Eğitim psikolojisi (Çeviri Editörü: Galip Yüksel) Ankara, Nobel Yayınları 10. Baskı. 115-137
28. Taşdemir, M. (2000). Eğitimde planlama ve değerlendirme. Ankara Ocak Yayınları.
29. Tchannen-Moran, M ve Woolfolk-Hoy, A. (2001). Teacher efficacy: Its meaning and measure. Review of Educational Research, 68 (2), 202-248.
30. Woolfolk, A. E. (1990). Educational psychology. New Jersey: Prentice Hall, Englewood Cliffs.

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